

Interoperability Guideline for TOSCA-based Deployable Services

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Abstract

This guideline proposes a set of extensions on the Deployment Service, Providers Portal, Service Registry and Front Office to enable service owners to make their services “deployable”. The guideline describes the modifications made in all the services involved in the description and deployment of the deployable templates based on the TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0 OASIS standard. It also provides service owners with relevant information to make their services deployable and available to the EOSC community.

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1. Intended Audience

The audience for the Guideline for TOSCA deployable services is:

- Service owners who want to make them deployable and available to the EOSC community.
- Any user who wants to use the EOSC Front Office to deploy a set of onboarded services in customized virtual infrastructures on multiple Cloud computing back-ends.

2. Description and main features

This guideline shows the set of extensions made on the EOSC Deployment Service, Providers Portal, Service Registry and Front Office to enable service owners to make their services “deployable”. A Deployable Service (DS) refers to a self-contained, orchestratable application or system described using TOSCA’s modelling constructs, which can be automatically deployed, configured, and managed on one or more target infrastructures (e.g. Cloud platforms). The guideline describes the modifications in all the services involved in the description and deployment of the deployable templates based on the TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0 OASIS standard [1].

3. Response to Community Need

Cloud infrastructures are appropriate platforms for addressing the computational needs of scientific applications. Users can customize the execution environment to their application needs through Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers. However, the use of public or on-premises Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) clouds requires users to have non-trivial system administration skills. This guideline will help service owners onboard deployable versions of their services that will enable users the deployment of services into Cloud virtual infrastructures, to have their own instance.

4. High-Level Service Architecture

A new Deployable Service profile¹ has been defined (see Annex A) to enable service owners to describe a service that can be automatically deployed via the EOSC Deployment Service, defined using the TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0 OASIS standard (see Table 4 for adopted standards).

Figure 1 shows a high-level view of the architecture and the interactions among the different services involved. The right part of the figure shows the onboard process of a Deployable Service (DS) in the platform. The left part shows the deployment process.

¹ <https://github.com/EOSC-PLATFORM/deployable-service-profile/>

Figure 1 - High-level architecture

The EOSC Deployment Service (powered by the Infrastructure Manager - IM²) implements a service that provides a REST API with a relatively simple set of functions, enabling the orchestration of cloud topologies. Cloud topologies can be described using the TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0 OASIS standard (see Table 1). The connection layer with Cloud providers is provided by the Cloud Connector layer, a set of connectors that interact with the particular API of each cloud provider, to add or remove resources. The configuration system, based on Ansible³, installs and configures all the requested software.

The EOSC Front Office is a catalogue that facilitates the exposure and discoverability of various types of resources, including the Deployable Services retrieved from the Service Catalogue. Providers of such services can specify user-configurable parameters within the EOSC Marketplace, such as the number of GPUs. End users can request the deployment of these services through the EOSC Marketplace by defining the parameters set by the provider and selecting the target cloud environment. Upon receiving a deployment request, the EOSC Front Office triggers a request to the Deployment Service, including the specified TOSCA template for the deployment. Once the deployment is complete, the Deployment Service returns the environment's access details to the EOSC Front Office, which then shares them with the end user.

The EOSC Service Registry offers the underlying storage functionality and interoperability tools for the programmatic access, registration, and management (CRUD) of providers, services, and catalogues. It also offers the necessary API functionality for the interoperability of service catalogues from individual providers or aggregators (e.g., thematic

² <https://www.grycap.upv.es/im>

³ <https://www.ansible.com>

or regional catalogues) with the EOSC portal. The EOSC Service Providers Dashboard/Portal enables the front-end functionality for the registration of EOSC Providers, organizations entitled to publish their resources via the EOSC Catalogue, and offers them capabilities to onboard and manage EOSC resources. It also offers the Providers Portal, where representatives from provider organizations have a detailed view of their offerings in the EOSC portal as well as various usage statistics on their resources. Finally, it offers to members of the onboarding team of the EOSC portal the functionality to manage the EOSC portal catalogue entries, i.e., manage the onboarding process of providers that apply to list their resources in the portal, audit the onboarded resources, etc.

5. Definitions

Acronym	Definition
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team
IM	Infrastructure Manager
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
RADL	Resource and Application Description Language
VM	Virtual Machine

Table 1 - Definitions

6. Licensing Information

The EOSC Deployment Service is powered by the Infrastructure Manager (IM) an open-source TOSCA-based Cloud Orchestrator distributed under version 3 of the GNU General Public License (GNU GPL-3.0).

The EOSC Front Office is released under the GNU General Public License version 3 (GPL-3.0).

The EOSC Service Registry and Providers Portal are released under the Apache 2.0 license.

7. Related Guidelines

This table outlines the guidelines related to the guideline being described in this document.

Resource Type	Title	Link
Service	EOSC Service Catalogue: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines	https://zenodo.org/records/8333871

Resource Type	Title	Link
Service	Order Management System Interoperability Guideline	https://zenodo.org/records/8375323

Table 2 – Related Guidelines

8. Adopted Standards

The following table describes the main standards, protocols, APIs, etc. adopted by the Deployment Service, with the intention to interoperate or integrate with the service.

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	relatedIdentifier
Protocol	IM REST API	A REST API is an API that conforms to the design principles of the REST, or Representational State Transfer architectural style	https://imdocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/REST.html
Standard	TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0	TOSCA version 1.0 specification is a YAML rendering which is intended to simplify the authoring of TOSCA service templates.	https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML/v1.0/csprd01/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML-v1.0-csprd01.html
Standard	OpenAPI 3.0	The IM API is compatible with the OpenAPI standard.	https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v3.0.0.html

Table 3 – Adopted Standards

9. Integration Options

This guideline outlines the process for onboarding a new Deployable Service in the catalogue, which can then be deployed, and for adding new deployable TOSCA templates to extend the current set of existing ones.

9.1. Onboard a deployable service

This integration allows onboarding a Deployable Service in the EOSC Service Catalogue using a newly defined profile.

9.2. Deploy an existing deployable service

This integration allows the deployment of a previously onboarded Deployable Service using the EOSC Front Office. It will also enable the management of the deployment lifecycle to finally delete it when it is no longer required.

9.3. Integrate new TOSCA-based Deployable Template

This integration enables the EOSC Deployment Service to deploy an additional set of templates that differ from those available in the Dashboard. This requires the definition of a new TOSCA Template.

10. Interoperability Guidelines

Please note that the Interoperability Guidelines are not intended to replace instruction manuals or help documentation.

10.1. Onboard deployable service

Service owners can either use the Service Registry API or access the Providers Portal UI to onboard a new deployable service, using the new Deployable Service profile. The onboarding flow is the same that is used for the onboarding of Services⁴:

- A user who needs to onboard a Deployable Service must first register as a Provider
- After registering as a Provider, the user can onboard a new Deployable Service by:
 - Using the REST API, or
 - Filling in the forms in the UI of the Providers Portal
- After submitting, the new Deployable Service is onboarded with a 'Pending' state. At this point, a review and approval from an EPOT team member is needed.
- When reviewed and approved, the Deployable Service is officially available to the Front Office.

10.2. Deploy an existing deployable service

Once a Deployable service has been onboarded in the Service Catalogue, it will appear in the Front Office, enabling any user to deploy a running instance of the particular service on a Cloud infrastructure that the user has access to. These are the steps needed to deploy a Deployable Service:

1. User discovers Deployable Services using full-text search and filters provided by the Front Office. Alternatively, users can also directly access the list of available Deployable Services at the Front Office's `/deployable_service` index page.
2. The Front Office gets the list of Deployable Services from the Service Catalogue (or from a database periodically synced with the Service Catalogue): The Front Office

⁴ For a full description on onboarding procedure of Services, please refer to <https://zenodo.org/records/8333871>

will fetch the TOSCA template from the Deployable Service URL parameter and will automatically generate an offer using the inputs section of the TOSCA template. It will finally show the offer to the user.

3. The user modifies the offer values. It will provide some default values that could fit in many cases, but the user can tune it to their particular needs (e.g., compute parameters: CPU, RAM, Disk). Additionally, other specific configuration options of the Deployable Service may be available, related to application-specific configuration.
4. Add information about the cloud provider. The user must provide credentials to access any cloud provider to deploy the service. In case of an EGI site, the name of the site (in GOCDB), a VO name supported in the site, and a valid EGI Check-in access token. If the Front Office uses EGI Check-in for the authentication, the same access token can be used. For other cloud providers, refer to IM documentation⁵ to see all the possible providers and required values.
5. Optionally, the user can also select a dataset to be staged in the cloud resources used for the Deployable service. In this case, the user will select a dataset providing a DOI.
6. Combining the TOSCA template obtained from the Deployable Service description with all the information provided by the user, the Front Office will generate a final version of the TOSCA template, also adding the required authentication information for the cloud provider [2].
7. Finally, the Front Office will call the Deployment Service to make the deployment.
8. Here, the request can be rejected by the Cloud Provider if there aren't enough resources available to actually deploy the service. The user will be notified with a "deployment failed" message and provided with the reason for the error.
9. If the request succeeds, the Front Office stores the returned Deployment ID and some other metadata (such as pending DNS of the deployed service if applicable).
10. Once the deployment has been successfully made, the Front Office will provide the TOSCA "outputs" with the needed information to access the newly deployed service. Typically, the output values return a URL with the endpoint of the deployed application, with some credentials needed to access it.

10.3.Lifecycle of a Deployable Service

The Front Office will also enable the management of the lifecycle of a Deployable Service:

- The Front Office will show the user the list of Deployable Service "deployments" made by the user. This list will display at least the ID of the deployment, the status and the TOSCA outputs (if a TOSCA template provides a "DNS" output, this will be highlighted for the user to directly access their deployed service).
- The Front Office will retrieve a list of all active deployments for a given user by querying the Deployment Service API, also fetching all output values of those deployments.

⁵ <https://imdocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/client.html#autho,therization-file>

- Finally, an option to delete the deployment will be shown in this list. In this case, the Front Office will call the Deployment Service to delete the deployment and release all the cloud resources created for the deployed service.

10.4. Integrate new TOSCA-based Deployable Template

To help service developers make their services deployable with the EOSC Deployment service, a new TOSCA template must be created that indicates the application architecture, computing and storage requirements, and relates to the corresponding recipes for performing automated software installation (typically via Ansible Roles). The service developers are offered two approaches:

- Simplified TOSCA Template: for users without a deep knowledge of TOSCA, this guideline defines a simplified version of the TOSCA standard that enables the deployment of a service using a minimal template that can be parameterized.
- TOSCA Template: If the user has knowledge about TOSCA or the available simplified TOSCA template does not fit the service requirements, a complete TOSCA template must be created.

10.4.1. Simplified TOSCA Template

The EOSC Deployment Service supports a simplification of the TOSCA YAML specification to facilitate developers in creating a simplified TOSCA template required to deploy their service on Cloud providers. They do not need to specify the complete TOSCA template. Instead, they just define a set of input values and links to pre-defined full TOSCA templates used to support common deployment strategies, such as deploying the application in a Virtual Machine or as a Docker container.

The set of input values defined in the linked TOSCA template can be specified in the simplified TOSCA document by setting the value as shown in the next template. These well-known and well-maintained full TOSCA templates will be stored in a git repository at https://github.com/grycap/tosca/tree/eosc_beyond, and only those can be referenced in the simplified TOSCA templates.

The simplified template has the following structure:

```
tosca_definitions_version: tosca_simple_yaml_1_0
imports:
  - template_file: base_template.yml
topology_template:
  inputs:
    input1: 2
    ...
    inputN: 4 GB
    ...
```

```
new_input:  
  type: string  
  description: New Input value
```

In this simplified template, the base template could be referenced using only the filename if the Deployment Service instance is preconfigured to use the EOSC-Beyond TOSCA repository by default. In other cases, the full URL of the base template must be specified: e.g.:

https://raw.githubusercontent.com/grycap/tosca/refs/heads/eosc_beyond/templates/base_template.yml

In addition to the set of input values defined in the linked TOSCA template, other new input values can be specified (for example, a value to set the password to access the application). In this case, they will be required to define the type⁶ and, optionally, a description.

Initial set of TOSCA Templates

There is a list of initial TOSCA templates that can be extended, as will be described in the next sections.

Single VM deployments

The simplest template is to deploy a single VM, where the service developer must provide the following set of input values to enable the service to be deployed.

Some of them are hardware-related values that are general for all single VM cases. These values are not mandatory in the service definition. Service owners can set it as an indication of the minimum values to set when deploying the service. These values could be changed by the user in the Front Office at deployment time.

- *num_cpus (integer)*: Minimum number of CPUs required.
- *mem_size (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of RAM required.
- *disk_size (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of Storage required.
- GPU requirements:
 - *num_gpus (integer)*: Number of GPUs.
 - *gpu_vendor (string)*: GPU vendor (AMD or NVIDIA).

The service must expose some ports to enable the users to access it. By default, single VM deployments expose HTTP and HTTPS ports, but if the service uses another set of ports, this input value must be set, specifying all the required ports:

- *ports*: Ports exposed by the application:
 - Map of elements with three elements:
 - *protocol (string)*: Protocol (TCP or UDP, default value TCP)
 - *Source (integer)*: Port number (mandatory)

⁶ See “3.2 Parameter and property types” of the OASIS TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0.

Also, a DNS name can be assigned to the VM to make easier access to it, also enabling the generation of valid TLS certificates to secure the HTTPS connection:

- *dns_name* (string): DNS name to assign to the deployed VM.

Regarding the DNS name, the Deployment Service is integrated with the EGI DyDNS service⁷. Therefore, any DNS name set in this parameter must use any of the registered domains at that service. Any reference to DNS names in the remaining templates described in this guideline will use the same service.

Other input fields depend on how the service software is distributed:

- Single container image:
 - *container_image* (string): Container image name (mandatory).
 - *environment* (map of strings): Environment Variables.
- Multiple container image:
 - *docker_compose* (string): Docker compose YAML file URL (mandatory)
 - *environment* (map of strings): Environment Variables.
- Ansible playbook:
 - *ansible_playbook*: URL of the ansible playbook to be executed in the instance to install the required service.
- Shell script:
 - *shell_script*: URL of the shell script to be executed in the instance to install the required service.
 - *shell_args*: arguments for the shell script to be executed in the instance installing the required service.

Finally, an outputs section is required to show the user the endpoints and/or credentials needed to access the deployed service. By default, the single VM template displays the node IP address and the SSH credentials for accessing the VM. In the following example, a URL of a service is added to the outputs section:

```
tosca_definitions_version: tosca_simple_yaml_1_0
imports:
  - template_file: single-vm.yml
topology_template:
  inputs:
# Set some recommended values
    num_cpus: 2
    mem_size: 4 GB
    disk_size: 20 GB
  ports:
```

⁷ <https://nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/>

```
    https_port:
      source: 443
  new_input:
    type: string
    description: New Input value
    default: some value
    required: true

# In case of container image
  container_image: python:3.10
  environment:
    PATH: /bin
    SOME_VAR: { get_input: new_input }

# In case of docker compose
  docker_compose: https://some.com/docker-compose.yaml
  environment:
    PATH: /bin

# In case of Ansible playbook
  ansible_playbook: https://some.com/ansible-playbook.yaml

# In case of shell script
  shell_script: https://some.com/shell.sh
  shell_args: "install -a"

outputs:
  service_endpoint:
    value:
      concat:
        - "https://"
        - { get_attribute: [ single_vm, public_address, 0 ] }
        - "/"
```

For example, the following TOSCA template deploys a GeoServer application, where the administrator password and the hardware inputs will be requested from the user before deploying the service.

```
tosca_definitions_version: tosca_simple_yaml_1_0
imports:
  - template_file: single-vm.yml
topology_template:
  inputs:
    admin_password:
      type: string
      description: GeoServer Admin user password

    container_image: docker.osgeo.org/geoserver:2.26.x
  environment:
    GEOSERVER_ADMIN_USER: "admin"
    GEOSERVER_ADMIN_PASSWORD: { get_input: admin_password }

  outputs:
    geoserver_url:
      value:
        concat:
          - "https://"
          - { get_input: dns_name }
          - "/geoserver"
```

Jupyter Notebook

In cases where applications require a Jupyter Notebook as the interface, this approach can be used.

As in the previous case, the first set of values is hardware-related values. These values are not mandatory. Service owners can set it as an indication of the recommended values to set when deploying the service. These values can be changed by the user in the Front Office at service deployment time.

- *num_cpus (integer)*: Minimum number of CPUs required.
- *mem_size (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of RAM required.
- *disk_size (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of Storage required.

- GPU requirements:
 - *num_gpus (integer)*: Number of GPUs.
 - *gpu_vendor (string)*: GPU vendor (AMD or NVIDIA).

Also, a DNS name can be assigned to the VM to make easier the access to it, also enabling the generation of valid TLS certificates to secure the HTTPS connection:

- *dns_name (string)*: DNS name to assign to the deployed VM.

The second set of values are Jupyter-specific. They enable the specification of the notebook image where the deployable service has been installed.

- *notebook_image (string)*: The notebook image. If not specified by default, it will use the *jupyter/base-notebook* image.
- *jupyter_token (string)*: The Jupyter token to access the Jupyter Web interface.

In this case, there will be two default outputs named "*jupyter_dns_url*" and "*jupyter_dns_ip*" that will show the URL of the Jupyter Web interface.

```
tosca_definitions_version: toska_simple_yaml_1_0
imports:
  - template_file: jupyter.yml
topology_template:
  inputs:
    num_cpus: 2
    mem_size: 4 GB
    disk_size: 20 GB

    jupyter_token: some_secure_token
    dns_name: somefancyname.vm.fedcloud.eu
```

Multiple VM deployments

In the case of multiple VM deployments, Kubernetes is the "de facto" standard for deploying microservices architectures. It will be used as the base deployed infrastructure to make the service available. In this case, the service owner must provide the following input values to enable the deployment of the service.

As in the single VM case, the first set of values are hardware-related values. Service owners can set it as an indication of the recommended values to set when deploying the service. These values could be changed by the user in the Front Office at the service deployment time.

- Front-End node properties:

- *fe_cpus (integer)*: Minimum number of CPUs required
- *fe_mem (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of RAM required
- *fe_disk_size (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of Storage required.
- Worker nodes properties:
 - *wn_num (integer)*: Number of Worker nodes.
 - *wn_cpus (integer)*: Minimum number of CPUs required
 - *wn_mem (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of RAM required
 - *wn_disk_size (scalar-unit)*: Minimum amount of Storage required.
 - GPU requirements:
 - *wn_num_gpus (integer)*: Number of GPUs
 - *wn_gpu_vendor (string)*: GPU vendor (AMD or NVIDIA).

Also, a DNS name can be assigned to the Kubernetes front-end to make it easier to access the deployed service endpoints, also enabling the generation of valid TLS certificates to secure the HTTPS connection:

- *dns_name (string)*: DNS name to assign to the deployed Kubernetes FE.

Other sets of values are Kubernetes-related. The template will set default values, but in case the service needs a specific Kubernetes version, it could be specified here:

- Kubernetes properties:
 - *kube_version (string)*: Kubernetes version: Version of Kubernetes to install

Other input fields depend on how the service software is distributed. In case of using a Helm chart:

- Helm chart:
 - From a Helm chart repo:
 - *helm_repo_name (string)*: Repository Name
 - *helm_repo_url (string)*: Repository URL
 - *helm_chart_name (string)*: Chart Name
 - *helm_chart_version (string)*: Chart Version
 - *helm_values (string)*: Contents of the values.yaml file as input for the helm install command.
 - From a chart compressed file:
 - *helm_chart_url (string)*: Chart URL
 - *helm_chart_name (string)*: Chart Name

In case of using a single YAML deployment file:

- YAML deployment file
 - *k8s_deploy_url* (*string*): URL of the file with the YAML file to deploy.

In this case, there will be a default output named “service_endpoint” that will show the URL of the “/” path of the ingress controller. So, if your application is available in the root path no output will be required; otherwise, you must overwrite it, as shown in the following example:

```
tosca_definitions_version: toska_simple_yaml_1_0
imports:
  - template_file: kubernetes.yml
topology_template:
  inputs:
    fe_cpus: 2
    fe_mem: 4 GB
    wn_num: 1
    wn_cpus: 2
    wn_mem: 4 GB

    kube_version: "1.30.4"
    dns_name: "myk8s.vm.fedlcloud.eu"

# In case of YAML deployments file
  k8s_deploy_url: ''

# In case of Helm chart
  helm_repo_name: ''
  helm_repo_url: ''
  helm_chart_url: ''
  helm_chart_name: ''
  helm_chart_version: ''
  helm_values: ''

  outputs:
    service_endpoint:
      value:
```

```
concat:  
- "https://"  
- { get_input: dns_name }  
- "/service_name"
```

10.4.2. Extending the list of available TOSCA Templates

Users can contribute to the list of TOSCA Templates by issuing a Pull Request to the repository of TOSCA Templates [3].

References

- [1] Palma, D., Rutkowski, M., Spatzier, T.: TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML version 1.0. OASIS Committee Specification 1, 20 (2016)
- [2] IM Documentation: Authorization File - <https://imdocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/client.html#authorization-file>
- [3] TOSCA Templates Repository. <https://github.com/grycap/tosca>